

DCPC news piece

What was the title of the event?

Digital Commons Policy Council Event

Where was it held?

Civic Health Innovation Labs, Liverpool

On what date and time?

21st-23rd May 2025

Who was invited?

Members of the [Digital Commons Policy Council](#) – Mathieu O’Neil (director) University of Canberra - Australia, Angela Daly (deputy director) University of Dundee - Scotland, Ramya Chandrasekhar, Riccardo Nanni, both National Centre for Scientific Research - France and Gary Leeming – Civic Data Cooperative Director.

A representative of the Cabinet Office Government Digital Service – Matthew Donnelly

A representative from the [Digital Commons Cooperative](#) – Colm Massey

Members of non-profit organisations focussed on responsible data usage, researchers with an interest in responsible data usage including political scientists, lawyers, and computer scientists, from India, Brazil, China, Uganda, Amsterdam & Norway.

We also invited applicants for sponsorship from LMIC for whom we organised travel and accommodation.

Who were the key speakers?

The meeting was mostly open discussion rather than presentations but there was a workshop from [NGI commons](#) led by Nicholas Gates, a policy advisor at OpenForum Europe on the Thursday afternoon.

What link did the event have to the university of Liverpool (i.e was it organised by senior UoL academics, were there any UoL staff speaking, was it affiliated with a centre?)

The event was organised by the [Civic Data Cooperative](#), a University of Liverpool-based research project funded by Liverpool City Region Combined Authority Combined Authority. Gary Leeming and Iain Buchan attended the event from University of Liverpool – CHIL.

How many people attended over the two days?

30 people attended in person and 5 people attended online (online participants were day 1 only).

What were the key aims of the event?

The main aim of the DCPC event held in May in Liverpool was to co-develop shared principles and policy frameworks for the governance of digital commons.

Participants worked collaboratively through breakout sessions and group discussions to agree on the outcomes of the meeting which were to:

1. Develop stakeholder engagement strategies

2. Define commons principles for governance of health data
3. Taxonomically describe digital commons
4. Define normative principles of digital commons.

Baseline documents were generated during the event and working groups convened that will continue to work together online to fully develop these outputs.

Do you have a comment/quote from a senior speaker or organiser we can include in the article regarding the event?

It was fantastic to bring together voices from across the world to look at the modern challenges around the open digital commons, from the Linux operating system through to Wikipedia and other open knowledge projects. By coming together to understand the policy needs around the world we hope that the outputs from this workshop will help governments and civil society understand the importance of this critical digital infrastructure and services that underpins and shapes so much of our lives – *Gary Leeming, CDC Director and DCPC member*